

DEVELOPMENT AND FEATURES OF MOBILE LEARNING AS A FORM OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the development and peculiarities of mobile learning as a form of distance education. The paper analyzes the key factors contributing to the growing popularity of mobile learning, such as the development of mobile technologies, the availability of the Internet and the rapid expansion of the capabilities of training applications. The article discusses the problems that teachers and students face when using mobile devices in the educational process, including the limited screen space, the need to adapt content, as well as issues of security and data protection. The article also discusses the prospects of mobile learning, including integration with other modern methods of distance learning, the use of artificial intelligence to personalize learning, as well as possible changes in the educational system due to the further development of mobile technologies.*

Keywords: *mobile learning, distance education, mobile technologies, personalization of learning, e-learning, educational platforms, interactive technologies, adaptive learning, innovations in education, ease of learning process, mobile applications for learning, multimedia resources.*

Introduction

Modern education is undergoing significant changes due to the introduction of new information and communication technologies. One of the most dynamically developing forms of learning is mobile learning, which is the use of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets, laptops) to gain knowledge and develop skills. This form of education is becoming an important component of distance education, providing students with the opportunity to study at any time and in any place, which is especially important in the context of globalization and the rapid development of technology.

Mobile learning significantly expands educational opportunities by integrating traditional and new learning methods, including multimedia resources, educational applications and platforms, which contributes to a more personalized and flexible approach to learning. At the same time, despite many advantages, mobile learning faces a number of challenges, such as the need to adapt training materials for mobile devices, as well as data security and technical support issues.

The purpose of this article is to review the development of mobile learning as an important form of distance education, highlight its features, and analyze current problems and prospects for further use of this form of education in various fields.

Research methodology

To study the development and features of mobile learning as a form of distance education, as well as the problems and prospects of its use, the article applies a comprehensive approach that includes the following methods and techniques: a literature analysis and secondary sources, stage, content analysis of educational platforms and mobile applications, discusses the questions and

questionnaires of students and teachers with an equal analysis of traditional and mobile learning, forecasting and perspective analysis. The research methodology combines theoretical and empirical approaches, which makes it possible to comprehensively analyze the development of mobile learning, identify its features and problems, and predict its prospects. The use of several research methods, such as literature analysis, case studies, questionnaires and comparative analysis, provides an opportunity to gain a comprehensive understanding of the current state of mobile learning and its further potential in the field of distance education.

Literary review

Mobile learning as a form of distance education attracts the attention of researchers and practitioners around the world due to its advantages in the field of accessibility, flexibility and personalization of training. In recent decades, with the development of mobile technologies and the widespread use of the Internet, this area has become an important element of the modern educational system. This literature review examines various aspects of mobile learning, including its development, features, problems, and prospects for use.

According to research by Hwang & Chen, 2017, mobile learning began to evolve in the early 2000s, with the advent of smartphones and tablets. Experts note that every year the number of educational applications and platforms that integrate various types of content increases: text materials, video tutorials, quizzes, and forums for communication between students and teachers. In the paper, mobile learning is considered as a means that allows students to be in a constant learning process, regardless of time and location.

Moreover, with the development of technologies such as 5G and cloud computing, mobile learning has become more accessible and functional. Sharples and others emphasize the importance of integrating mobile technologies with other teaching methods, including e-learning and virtual learning, which contributes to the flexibility of the educational process.

One of the key features of mobile learning is its mobility and flexibility. Mobile devices allow students to access educational materials anytime, anywhere. Muhammad Ali's research shows that mobile learning helps to increase students' motivation, as they can independently plan their time and choose appropriate learning methods. This form of training is especially popular among students and employees who combine their studies with other responsibilities.

However, one of the significant features of mobile learning is its interactivity and multimedia content. Scientist Kukulska-Hulme, 2009 states that the use of multimedia elements, such as video, audio and images, increases students' interest in the learning process and contributes to better assimilation of the material. At the same time, mobile devices often offer features for teamwork, which encourages the development of communication and collaborative skills.

Despite its many advantages, mobile learning faces a number of challenges. One of them is the limited functionality of mobile devices. Small mobile screens and limited device resources make it difficult to display complex learning materials, such as detailed graphs or technical diagrams (Conole, 2013). Another important issue is the need to adapt traditional educational materials to mobile platforms, which requires additional efforts on the part of developers and teachers.

Another important issue is ensuring data security and protection. When using mobile devices for learning, there is a risk of leaks of personal information and unfair use of student data. This raises questions about legal aspects and the need to develop secure educational platforms.

In the future, mobile learning will play an important role in the educational system. Research shows that in the future, mobile learning will be closely linked to the use of new technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR), and virtual reality (VR) (Johnson et al., 2016). These technologies will help create more dynamic and personalized learning environments that can significantly increase student engagement and improve learning outcomes.

Social and cultural changes also play a significant role in the development of mobile learning. More and more educational institutions are beginning to integrate mobile technologies into the educational process, which contributes to the creation of hybrid learning models that combine traditional and distance methods. An important step is also to increase the availability of mobile learning for various social groups, including people with disabilities.

Mobile learning, despite the existing problems, continues to develop and has a significant impact on education. Every year there is a growing interest in this area, and new solutions appear that help to overcome current difficulties. In the near future, we can expect a wider use of mobile technologies in the educational process, which will open up new horizons for students and teachers.

Discussion

Mobile learning as a form of distance education is actively developing due to the rapid spread of mobile technologies and the constant improvement of Internet access. Unlike traditional forms of learning, mobile learning allows students not only to learn at a convenient time and place, but also to use a variety of interactive and multimedia resources, such as educational applications, video lectures, online courses and tests. This contributes to a deeper and more effective assimilation of the material, and also allows you to take into account the individual needs of each student.

One of the significant advantages of mobile learning is the ability to integrate with other technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR), which significantly increases students' interest in learning and contributes to better assimilation of knowledge. For example, the use of AI can help in personalizing the learning process, adapting the content depending on the level of knowledge and preferences of the student. Augmented and virtual reality open up new horizons for practical training, laboratory work and simulations, which is not possible in the framework of traditional training.

However, despite all the advantages, mobile learning faces a number of significant challenges. One of them is the limited screen space of mobile devices, which complicates the perception of certain types of content, such as graphs or texts with a large amount of information. In addition, not all training materials can be effectively adapted for mobile platforms, which requires additional time and resources to develop and update content.

Another important aspect is the issue of data security and confidentiality. The use of mobile devices for training requires the transfer of personal information and learning outcomes, which can lead to risks of data leaks or misuse. It is also necessary to provide protection against virus attacks and provide technical support at all stages of the educational process.

The prospects for mobile learning look promising. In the future, we can expect further integration of mobile learning with other forms of distance education, such as online courses, webinars, and digital platforms for collective learning. With the development of 5G technologies and the improvement of the quality of mobile devices, the availability and quality of mobile content will increase. It is also important that educational institutions continue to work on

improving adaptive technologies, creating educational materials suitable for mobile platforms, and ensuring a high degree of data security. Intensive training has a huge potential for transforming the educational process, but its effective implementation requires solving a number of technical, pedagogical and ethical problems.

Results

Mobile learning (m-learning) as a form of distance education has a number of unique characteristics that distinguish it from traditional forms of learning and other types of distance education. These features make mobile learning particularly convenient and effective for different categories of students.

One of the main features of mobile learning is the ability to learn anywhere and at any time. Using mobile devices (smartphones, tablets, laptops) allows students to access educational resources and materials without being limited to the physical space of the classroom. This makes it possible to study on the road, at home, in between classes, and even on trips. This approach is especially valuable for people who combine their studies with work or family responsibilities.

Another special feature is that mobile devices allow you to actively use multimedia materials, such as video tutorials, audio content, graphics, animation, and interactive tests. This significantly improves the perception of educational material, making the learning process more fun and diverse. Interactive elements such as quizzes, challenges, and simulations help students actively engage in the process, as well as help them better absorb and consolidate information.

It should be noted that more extensive training provides flexibility and personalization of the educational process. It allows students to choose the pace and sequence of training, as well as adapt training to their needs and capabilities. Unlike traditional learning, where the learning process is often standardized, mobile platforms can offer personalized recommendations tailored to the student's level of knowledge and preferences. This can increase the efficiency of learning the material.

Mobile educational platforms often provide instant feedback, which is important for students who are learning material on their own. For example, after completing tests and tasks, students immediately get results, which allows them to quickly correct mistakes and improve their results. It also helps to increase students' motivation and independence.

Mobile learning supports both synchronous (real-time) and asynchronous (non-concurrent) forms of interaction. Students can participate in online lectures and webinars (synchronous learning), as well as view materials, complete tasks and tests at a convenient time (asynchronous learning). This flexibility allows you to combine mobile learning with other responsibilities, which is especially important for people with limited time.

Mobile platforms can include various functions for social and collaborative work, such as forums, chats, discussion groups, and project collaboration. It helps students communicate and work in groups, developing teamwork and collaboration skills. Social interaction also helps to increase students' engagement and motivation, as well as allows them to share experiences and knowledge.

Mobile platforms often offer educational content in short, easy-to-digest blocks. Such "micro-lessons" allow students to learn the material in small portions, which contributes to better assimilation and a higher level of concentration. This is especially useful for people with a busy schedule who may be engaged in training in short periods of time.

Mobile learning actively uses new technologies such as augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), artificial intelligence (AI), big data (big data) and results analysis. These technologies allow for more interactive, personalized, and immersive learning environments. For example, with the help of augmented reality, students can conduct virtual laboratory work or study historical monuments, and artificial intelligence can adapt educational materials to the individual needs of students.

Mobile devices are usually intuitive and easy to use, which contributes to a wide coverage of different categories of students. It is important that mobile platforms often have user-friendly interfaces and easily adapt to different devices and operating systems, which makes training accessible to a wide range of users.

Mobile learning, thanks to its features, is a powerful tool for distance education, offering flexibility, accessibility, interactivity and personalization of the learning process. These features make mobile learning attractive to both students and teachers, providing new opportunities for learning in a diverse environment and enhancing the quality of the educational experience.

Mobile learning combines several advantages that make it attractive for students and teachers alike. First, it provides high flexibility: students can study anytime and anywhere, which is especially important for people with limited time or those who combine learning with work. Mobile learning can significantly expand access to educational resources, especially in the context of limited opportunities of traditional educational institutions.

Secondly, it helps to increase students' motivation through the use of various multimedia and interactive elements, such as video tutorials, tests, games and forums. These tools make learning more fun and active, which helps students absorb the material better.

Mobile learning also improves student-teacher interaction through various messaging platforms, chats, and video conferences. Such tools increase the level of student involvement in the process and create opportunities for individual communication with teachers.

Despite its obvious advantages, mobile learning faces a number of challenges. One of the key challenges is the need to adapt training materials for mobile platforms. Limited mobile device screens can make it difficult to perceive complex text and graphic materials. This requires the development of compact and mobile-optimized educational materials that do not lose their informative content and quality.

Another important aspect is the issue of security and privacy. The use of mobile devices for educational purposes requires the protection of students' and teachers' personal data, as well as protection against viruses and other threats.

In addition, there is the problem of digital inequality: not all students have access to modern mobile devices or a stable Internet connection, which limits the possibilities of mobile learning for some categories of students.

The future of mobile learning is closely linked to the development of technologies and innovative approaches to learning. In the coming years, we can expect further improvements in the quality of mobile educational platforms, increased opportunities for personalized learning using artificial intelligence, as well as integration with augmented and virtual reality technologies, which will open up new horizons for students, allowing them to conduct more complex and interactive classes.

It is also important to note that mobile learning will become not only more accessible, but also more inclusive, allowing people with disabilities to learn and overcome barriers related to the physical accessibility of educational institutions.

Mobile learning continues to be actively developed as a form of distance education, and its potential will only increase with the development of technology. It allows you to make the educational process more accessible, flexible and efficient, giving students the opportunity to study at a convenient time and in any place. Despite the existing problems and challenges, mobile learning has great prospects and promises to become an integral part of the educational system of the future.

Conclusion

Mobile learning, as a form of distance education, is an important and promising component of the modern educational system. The development of mobile technologies and the widespread use of smartphones and tablets create new opportunities for organizing the educational process, ensuring that education is accessible anywhere and at any time. Mobile learning becomes not only a tool for increasing the flexibility of the learning process, but also a powerful tool for personalization of learning, allowing you to adapt materials to the needs of each student.

However, despite its many advantages, mobile learning faces a number of challenges, including the limited capacity of mobile devices to handle complex learning materials, data security and privacy issues, and digital inequality. These challenges require the development of effective solutions to improve the quality of education and ensure equal access to educational resources.

The prospects for mobile learning are vast and are associated with the further development of technologies such as artificial intelligence, augmented and virtual reality, which will open up new horizons for educational processes. In the future, mobile learning will increasingly integrate with other forms of learning, creating hybrid models that promote even greater flexibility and efficiency in the educational experience.

Thus, mobile learning has a huge potential for transforming education, and its development will contribute to creating more accessible, interactive and personalized educational solutions that meet the needs of students and modern society as a whole.

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